

DeepSky dataset: A new benchmark for ground-based cloud classification using all-sky images

Dimitrios Tsourounis¹, Dimitris Kastaniotis¹, Panagiotis Tzoumanikas², George Andrianakos³, Orestis Panagopoulos², Andreas Kazantzidis², Christos Theocharatos³, and George Economou¹

¹ *Electronics Laboratory, Physics Department, University of Patras, Rio Patras, 26504, Greece,*

² *Laboratory of Atmospheric Physics, Physics Department, University of Patras, Rio Patras, 26504 Greece,*

³ *Irida Labs, Patras InnoHub – Kastritsiou 4, Magoula Patras, 26504, Greece*

Abstract

Cloud observation methods have attracted growing interest due to their significant role in climate prediction and weather forecasting applications since clouds serve as important indicators of weather conditions. Ground-based cloud image classification, which involves categorizing all-sky images into predefined classes, is a key approach to address this challenge. Deep learning methods have demonstrated their effectiveness in various computer vision tasks; however, their performance is inherently tied to the size and quality of the dataset employed for training and evaluation. Many ground-based all-sky image datasets are available, each fulfilling various criteria, including the number of samples, the duration of data collection, the interval between collected samples, the geographical location of data collection, the resolution of images, the types of sky images, and the annotation process used to assign labels to the images. In this paper, we introduce the DeepSky dataset, a novel ground-based all-sky image classification dataset captured over a span of two years. The dataset comprises over seven thousand images and includes seven cloud categories, making it one of the largest datasets in the field. Additional to the dataset, we present an effective cloud classification model based on SWIN Transformers, which achieves state-of-the-art accuracy when evaluated to the other large all-sky image dataset. We are confident that the new dataset, the analysis on cross-dataset evaluation, and the transformer-based proposed method will provide researchers with new opportunities and challenges to explore and expand upon in their investigations. The dataset and supplementary code materials can be accessed from: <https://github.com/dimkastan/DeepSky-classification-dataset>.

Keywords: ground-based cloud observation, all-sky images, cloud classification, deep learning

1 Introduction

Clouds observation plays a crucial role in numerous applications, including weather forecasting, climate research as well as environmental monitoring. Cloud observations can be classified into space-based remote sensing, where satellites capture images of the Earth's atmosphere from above. Additionally, ground-based observations can be obtained using various sky imaging techniques.

These techniques produce different types of sky images, including sky patch images (SPIs), total sky images (TSIs), and all-sky images (ASIs). The SPIs are captured using wide-angle lenses, resulting in images that cover a portion of the sky instead of the entire sky thole. On the other hand, TSIs are obtained by utilizing a hemispherical chrome-plated mirror to reflect the sky onto a camera positioned above the mirror. However, these images often have low resolution and are hindered by a black sun-blocking shadow band and camera supporting arm, limiting the view of the entire sky. ASIs are typically acquired using a camera equipped with a fish-eye lens, enabling a detailed view

Figure 1: Examples of images from the DeepSky dataset, showcasing the seven different cloud categories.

of the whole sky dome. Ultimately, each type of sky image offers unique features and insights into cloud formations, catering to specific user requirements.

Labeling sky images with relevant information is a crucial aspect that enhances their usability across various applications. For example, incorporating irradiance and photovoltaic power generation data enables the study of clouds impact on solar energy production while segmentation maps, which delineate cloud boundaries, are useful for analyzing cloud morphology and tracking cloud movements. Cloud category labels provide insights into cloud dynamics and their impact on weather patterns. Some of these labeled data are derived from additional measurement instruments, while others require human annotation. Nonetheless, their utilization facilitates researchers to explore a wide range of research questions and develop more comprehensive models for cloud observation.

Over the past decade, significant progress has been made in developing data-driven algorithms for the automated analysis of cloud formations in the sky (Taravat et al., 2015). Although the continuous progress of learning models through new proposed topologies and methods, ranging from hand-crafted techniques (Cheng & Yu, 2015; Dev et al., 2015; Gan et al., 2017; Q. Li et al., 2016; Oikonomou et al., 2019; Xiao et al., 2016) to Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) (M. Li et al., 2019; S. Liu, Li, Zhang, Xiao, et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2017; Tsourounis et al., 2022; Ye et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2022), Graph CNNs (S. Liu et al., 2022; S. Liu, Li, Zhang, Cao, et al., 2020a), and Transformers (X. Li et al., 2022), their success heavily relies on the availability of high-quality and diverse datasets for training and evaluation. Cloud formation is influenced by multiple natural factors, resulting in regional and seasonal variations, making localization criteria important. The geographic location and the collection period also impact the images captured by cameras due to local environmental conditions. Additionally, the camera specifications and settings introduce additional challenges. Therefore, the creation of new all-sky datasets containing thousands of images helps capturing a wider range of characteristics, further enhancing the development of cloud analysis methods. Furthermore, the presence of multiple cloud image datasets facilitates the evaluation of feature transferability across various cloud classification tasks. It enables researchers to analyze how well features learned from one dataset and generalize to another, providing insights into the models' adaptability and transfer learning capabilities. Moreover, the existence of diverse datasets enables sophisticated error analysis, allowing for in-depth exploration and understanding of the limitations and challenges faced by current algorithms. This comprehensive analysis helps in driving advancements in the field by identifying areas for improvement and inspiring the development of innovative solutions.

To the best of our knowledge, the largest publicly available ground-based all-sky image dataset with cloud category labels is the Ground-based Remote Sensing Cloud Database (TJNU-GRSCD) (S. Liu, Li, Zhang, Cao, et al., 2020b). This dataset collected in Tianjin by the Meteorological Observation Centre of the China Meteorological Administration for the task of cloud image classification. It contains all-sky colored images captured using a fisheye lens, with a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels in color JPEG format. The dataset spans from 2017 to 2018 and consists of 8000 images, with 4000 for training and 4000 for testing. The images are divided into seven sky types according to the presented clouds: 1) cumulus, 2) altocumulus and cirrocumulus, 3) cirrus and cirrostratus, 4) clear sky, 5) stratocumulus, stratus, and altostratus, 6) cumulonimbus and nimbostratus, 7) mixed cloudiness, following the international cloud classification system criteria published in the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) as well as the visual similarity of cloud in practice. The distinguishing features of the GRSCD include its significantly larger number of all-sky images and the provision of separate training and test sets compared to other available datasets (Nie et al., 2022).

This work introduces a new dataset specifically curated for cloud classification using all-sky images. The dataset covers a wide range of weather conditions, cloud types, and atmospheric phenomena, spanning a two-year period. Our main contribution lies in creating a benchmark dataset to facilitate robust and accurate cloud classification models that generalize well in real-world scenarios. State-of-the-art (sota) deep learning models, including the ResNet-50 CNN and Swin Transformer, are evaluated to establish baseline performance on the new dataset. The presented dataset is categorized among the two largest all-sky image datasets with cloud category labels, sharing an equivalent number of images. Also, the two datasets share the same cloud categories and thus, a comparative analysis could be conducted between them. Finally, the proposed transformer-based approach achieves state-of-the-art performance, surpassing previous best results on the GRSCD.

2 Proposed Method

The contribution of the proposed method is two-fold. Firstly, a new dataset is introduced, facilitating the evaluation of different approaches using various evaluation criteria, including cross-dataset generalization using existing datasets. Secondly, a voting scheme is presented, which improves the models' performance by 1%, simply applying augmentations on the test images and utilizing majority voting to determine the final classification prediction.

2.1 DeepSky dataset

The DeepSky dataset collected using a Mobotix Q26B-6D016 hemispheric camera with a fisheye lens B016 (focal length 1.6 mm, $f/2.0$, $180^\circ \times 180^\circ$), featuring a $1/1.8''$ CMOS, 6MP (3072×2048), Progressive Scan on 1024×768 resolution, and stored in 24-bit color JPEG format along. A Circle of Interest (COI) with a fixed radius set at 324 pixels is defined to ensure that the analysis focuses solely on relevant cloud information. Then, the images are cropped to the final size of 678×678 pixels, removing the black space of COI surrounding the image. Some image examples are shown on Figure 1. The distribution of samples across the recording time is presented in the following Figure 2. The system was captured samples only during daytime to avoid recording samples to ensure visibility of cloudiness in the images. The images were annotated by professional meteorologists to assign the dominant cloud category in each image. Although the system acquires one image per 11 seconds, we selected approximately one image per 30 minutes to form the dataset. Considering that the recordings span a period of two years, we found prominent to split the training and test data in a yearly basis. Towards this goal, the recordings from 2021 were utilized for training and validation, while the recordings from 2022 were reserved for testing. For the training and validation split, researchers have the flexibility to employ various cross-validation approaches; however, we recommend employing the Leave N samples out method, with N set to 10% of the training data across all categories. The test set represents a projection into future events, encompassing potential natural deviations that may not be evident within short time intervals. By doing so, we aim to provide a more accurate reflection of the true distribution of cloud formations, thereby enhancing the reliability and generalizability of classification models.

Figure 2: Distributions of images in the DeepSky dataset.

The variation in the number of images per class can be attributed to the geographical environmental conditions of the camera's operation, as different cloud categories are closely linked to the climate of camera's location. To ensure a balanced training set, suitable for end-to-end data-driven learning methods, the training set is carefully pre-processed. Cloud categories that are overrepresented, such as the clear sky class is reduced by randomly selecting a subset of images. On the other hand, underrepresented categories, like cumulonimbus and mixed clouds, are enlarged following two approaches respectively for the two classes. The visual characteristics of cumulonimbus images enable us to increase the sampling rate and select images at 15-minute intervals on days when cumulonimbus clouds are present, while still maintaining the diversity of this class. The mixed class comprises images with multiple clouds, making it a combination of some of other cloud categories. To enhance its representation, image blending techniques are applied using training images from different cloud categories within the dataset. A human expert then selects the most photorealistic output images for inclusion in the mixed class. Consequently, the mixed training class is an amalgam of original and synthetic images. Detailed metadata accompanies the original and synthetic images within the dataset to provide comprehensive information about the blended images. A detailed description the dataset is presented on Table 1.

2.2 Swin Transformer and TTA

In this study, we employ Vision Transformers, and specifically the Swin Transformers (Z. Liu et al., 2021), for the image classification task. The Swin Transformers are chosen due to their distinctive architecture, combining the advantages of processing both local and global information. Through the utilization of hierarchical shifting windows, these transformers effectively capture local dependencies while concurrently enabling the incorporation of larger receptive fields to capture global spatial context. This adaptability empowers the models to effectively comprehend and model input patterns, ultimately leading to superior generalization performance across tasks and datasets. Given the inherent characteristics of all-sky image classification, which necessitates the capture of long-range spatial context, the transformers emerge as the most suitable approach for this specific task. Furthermore, demonstrate that by leveraging transformers in conjunction with a Test-Time Augmentation (TTA) technique (Shanmugam et al., 2020), we can achieve an additional improvement in classification performance.

When working with all-sky images, it is important to consider their specific limitations when applying augmentations. It is not recommended to use colour augmentations without careful consideration, as they can potentially modify the cloud characteristics and impact the assigned cloud category. Furthermore, cropping images could isolate parts of clouds or even exclude clouds entirely, which may not align with the assigned class label of the image. Hence, it is crucial to employ augmentation techniques that maintain the original cloud category in the images. Taking into consideration these observations, the TTA pipeline follows 12 equally spaced image rotations. Additionally, for each rotated version of the image, a five-crop strategy is implemented, where only 10% of the image boundaries are cropped. The total number of 60 images is passed from the network and the classification decisions are incorporated through majority voting. The query image is then classified into the category that receives the highest number of votes.

Classes - Cloud type	Description	Year	
		2021	2022
1. <i>Cumulus</i>	Puffy clouds	661	610
2. <i>Alto cumulus</i>	Alto cumulus & Cirro cumulus	464	521
3. <i>Cirrus</i>	Cirrus & Cirro stratus	559	572
4. <i>Clear sky</i>	Cloudless or a very few cloudiness	655	601
5. <i>Strato cumulus</i>	Strato cumulus, Stratus, & Alto stratus	431	570
6. <i>Cumulonimbus</i>	Cumulonimbus & Nimbo stratus	568	266
7. <i>Mixed</i>	More than two genera of clouds	645	185
Total		3983	3325

Table 1: DeepSky dataset, Number of images per class and per year.

3 Experimental Results

Our experimental analysis focuses on three main aspects. First, we evaluate the performance of the SWIN transformers and TTA method on the GRSCD dataset. Second, we present the performance of this method on the new DeepSky dataset. Third, we compare the transferability between the two datasets.

All models were trained using PyTorch on a Linux machine with four NVIDIA GPUs GeForce RTX 2080 with 8GB. The SWIN base transformer was trained with input image size of 224×224 pixels, patch size of 4 pixels and window size of 7 pixels, which achieves the best performance surpassing by almost 2% the ResNet-50 on the GRSCD classification problem. The SWIN transformer was trained with a cosine learning rate scheduler and a starting learning rate of 0.001. The image augmentations were designed to take into consideration the limitations imposed by the annotation and task definition, as described in the previous section, and thus, images were only rotated and color-augmented with color jitter parameters that do not heavily alter the images.

3.1 Intra-dataset analysis

During our experiments, we found that the SWIN base Transformer combined with TTA surpasses all previous methods in the GRSCD, as demonstrated in Table 2. This can be attributed to the expressive capabilities of Transformer networks and their inherent ability to learn high-level relationships between different regions of the image. For the task of all-sky image classification, the attention mechanism in Transformers plays a crucial role in preserving local information and effectively associating it with other regions. This is particularly important as different cloud formations can coexist in the image, along with parts of clear sky. Additionally, Table 2 presents baseline results for the newly introduced DeepSky dataset using ResNet-50 and SWIN Transformer.

Figure 3 presents the confusion matrices for the best performing method on both datasets. The mixed cloudiness class poses the greatest challenge, as it is often confused with multiple other categories, as expected. On the DeepSky dataset, the accuracy for the mixed class is relatively low; however, individual cloud categories within the mixed cloudiness are still detected in the images, suggesting that a post-processing mechanism could be beneficial for this particular class, but it is beyond the scope of this work. Moreover, the DeepSky dataset shows a higher level of confusion between stratocumulus and cumulonimbus images, given their similar texture structure. In the GRSCD, the cirrus images are primarily confused with the mixed category, consistent with findings in the relevant literature (M. Li et al., 2019).

References	Method	Accuracy (%)
GRSCD		
(S. Liu, Li, Zhang, Xiao, et al., 2020)	SIFT + BoW	66.13
(S. Liu, Li, Zhang, Xiao, et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2018)	CloudNet	79.92
(S. Liu, Li, Zhang, Xiao, et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2017)	DCAFs	82.67
(M. Li et al., 2019)	ResNet-50 + DGL	85.28
(S. Liu, Li, Zhang, Xiao, et al., 2020)	ResNet-50 + Attentive Net	86.25
(Tsourounis et al., 2022)	Fusion: ResNet-18 & SIFT-ResNet-18	87.22
(S. Liu, Li, Zhang, Cao, et al., 2020b)	TGCNN (with ResNet-50)	89.48
(Zhu et al., 2022)	Fusion: ICN, ResNet-50 & VGG-16	90.08
Ours	ResNet-50 + TTA	89.12
Ours	SWIN transformer	90.25
Ours	SWIN transformer + TTA	91.25
DeepSky dataset		
Ours	ResNet-50 + TTA	76.32
Ours	SWIN transformer + TTA	76.83

Table 2: Classification accuracy using sota methods on GRSCD and DeepSky datasets.

Figure 3: Confusion matrices using SWIN transformer + TTA, evaluated on GRSCD and DeepSky datasets.

3.2 Cross-dataset analysis

It is crucial to assess the generalization ability of a model trained on one dataset when applied on the other. To investigate this, we employed the trained models on one dataset and evaluated their performance on a new dataset, as shown in Table 3 and the accompanying confusion matrices in Figure 4. The results reveal substantial differences between the two datasets. Particularly, when training on the GRSCD and evaluating on the DeepSky dataset, a performance drop of about 10% was observed compared to training on the DeepSky dataset. Conversely, when training on the DeepSky dataset and evaluating on the GRSCD dataset, a drop of over 20% was observed. These findings emphasize the disparities between the two datasets and highlight the challenges in generalizing models from one dataset to another, even when they share similar classes. Furthermore, we are investigating the impact of learning the joint distribution of the dataset by merging the training sets of both the GRSCD and DeepSky datasets. Subsequently, we evaluate the model's performance on each individual test set. This approach enables us to assess the extent to which the model possesses the capability to learn from multiple distributions. From the results presented in Table 3, it is evident that the GRSCD can improve the performance on the DeepSky as the joint distribution allows the model to learn some common characteristics across datasets. Also, as shown in the confusion matrices in Figure 4, some characteristics from one dataset are transferred to the other, as for example the performance on the mixed category on GRSCD comparing results from Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Method	Trained on	Evaluated on	Accuracy (%)
Swin Transformer + TTA	Cross-dataset		
	DeepSky	GRSCD	68.75
	GRSCD	DeepSky	66.35
	Both-datasets		
	GRSCD + DeepSky	GRSCD	86.27
GRSCD + DeepSky	DeepSky	77.14	

Table 3: Investigation using cross dataset analysis and using jointly both training sets.

Figure 4: Confusion matrices (True Response vs. Predicted Response) using SWIN transformer + TTA. Upper left: Trained on DeepSky, evaluated on GRSCD. Upper right: Trained on GRSCD, evaluated on DeepSky. Down left: Trained on both, evaluated on GRSCD. Down right: Trained on both, evaluated on DeepSky.

By employing a feature extraction technique using a ResNet-50 model pretrained on ImageNet, we generated biplots that allow for visual analysis of the data distribution. The penultimate fully connected layer output served as the feature vector, and t-SNE was utilized to project these vectors into a 2-dimensional space. Through this approach, we can examine the distribution of the newly introduced DeepSky dataset and its relationship with the GRSCD. The visualization of Figure 5 clearly reveals that the DeepSky dataset exhibits a more uniform distribution, in contrast to the GRSCD, which shows distinct trajectories. In this manner, the DeepSky dataset features a more spherical distribution as compared to the GRSCD, where specific clusters are appeared both on its training and test sets.

Figure 5: Feature vector embedding from GRSCD (crosses) and DeepSky dataset (circles) in 2D space.

4 Conclusions

In this work we focused on the problem of all-sky image classification and proposed a straightforward yet powerful approach utilizing Transformers and Test Time Augmentations. Furthermore, we introduced a novel dataset consisting of recordings spanning two years. This dataset allows for comprehensive evaluations of model generalization and learning capabilities across datasets, particularly considering that the DeepSky dataset shares cloud types with the GRSCD. Notably, the DeepSky and GRSCD datasets are currently the largest existing all-sky datasets with cloud category labels. Future plans include the extension of the DeepSky dataset using both the images of next year and additional environmental multimodal information. Additionally, we aim to explore the utilization of image sequences to train Transformer-based architectures, further enhancing the performance of our models.

Acknowledgements

This research has been co-financed by the European Union and Greek national funds through the Operational Program Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation, under the call RESEARCH – CREATE – INNOVATE (project code: T1EDK – 00681, MIS 5067617).

References

- Cheng, H.-Y., & Yu, C.-C. (2015). Block-based cloud classification with statistical features and distribution of local texture features. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 8(3), 1173–1182. <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-8-1173-2015>
- Dev, S., Lee, Y. H., & Winkler, S. (2015). Categorization of cloud image patches using an improved texton-based approach. *2015 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, 422–426. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIP.2015.7350833>
- Gan, J., Lu, W., Li, Q., Zhang, Z., Yang, J., Ma, Y., & Yao, W. (2017). Cloud Type Classification of Total-Sky Images Using Duplex Norm-Bounded Sparse Coding. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 10(7), 3360–3372. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSTARS.2017.2669206>
- Li, M., Liu, S., & Zhang, Z. (2019). Dual Guided Loss for Ground-Based Cloud Classification in Weather Station

- Networks. *IEEE Access*, 7, 63081–63088. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2916905>
- Li, Q., Zhang, Z., Lu, W., Yang, J., Ma, Y., & Yao, W. (2016). From pixels to patches: A cloud classification method based on a bag of micro-structures. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 9(2), 753–764. <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-9-753-2016>
- Li, X., Qiu, B., Cao, G., Wu, C., & Zhang, L. (2022). A Novel Method for Ground-Based Cloud Image Classification Using Transformer. *Remote Sensing*, 14(16), Article 16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14163978>
- Liu, S., Duan, L., Zhang, Z., Cao, X., & Durrani, T. S. (2022). Ground-Based Remote Sensing Cloud Classification via Context Graph Attention Network. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 60, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2021.3063255>
- Liu, S., Li, M., Zhang, Z., Cao, X., & Durrani, T. S. (2020b). Ground-Based Cloud Classification Using Task-Based Graph Convolutional Network. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 47(5). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL087338>
- Liu, S., Li, M., Zhang, Z., Xiao, B., & Durrani, T. S. (2020). Multi-Evidence and Multi-Modal Fusion Network for Ground-Based Cloud Recognition. *Remote Sensing*, 12(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12030464>
- Liu, Z., Lin, Y., Cao, Y., Hu, H., Wei, Y., Zhang, Z., Lin, S., & Guo, B. (2021). Swin Transformer: Hierarchical Vision Transformer using Shifted Windows. *2021 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 9992–10002. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCV48922.2021.00986>
- Nie, Y., Li, X., Paletta, Q., Aragon, M., Scott, A., & Brandt, A. (2022). *Open-Source Ground-based Sky Image Datasets for Very Short-term Solar Forecasting, Cloud Analysis and Modeling: A Comprehensive Survey* (arXiv:2211.14709). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2211.14709>
- Oikonomou, S., Kazantzidis, A., Economou, G., & Fotopoulos, S. (2019). A local binary pattern classification approach for cloud types derived from all-sky imagers. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 40(7), 2667–2682. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2018.1530807>
- Shanmugam, D., Blalock, D. W., Balakrishnan, G., & Gutttag, J. V. (2020). Better Aggregation in Test-Time Augmentation. *2021 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 1194–1203.
- Shi, C., Wang, C., Wang, Y., & Xiao, B. (2017). Deep Convolutional Activations-Based Features for Ground-Based Cloud Classification. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 14(6), 816–820. <https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2017.2681658>
- Taravat, A., Del Frate, F., Cornaro, C., & Vergari, S. (2015). Neural Networks and Support Vector Machine Algorithms for Automatic Cloud Classification of Whole-Sky Ground-Based Images. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, 12(3), 666–670. <https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2014.2356616>
- Tsourounis, D., Kastaniotis, D., Theoharatos, C., Kazantzidis, A., & Economou, G. (2022). SIFT-CNN: When Convolutional Neural Networks Meet Dense SIFT Descriptors for Image and Sequence Classification. *Journal of Imaging*, 8(10), Article 10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jimaging8100256>
- Xiao, Y., Cao, Z., Zhuo, W., Ye, L., & Zhu, L. (2016). mCLOUD: A Multiview Visual Feature Extraction Mechanism for Ground-Based Cloud Image Categorization. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 33(4), 789–801. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JTECH-D-15-0015.1>
- Ye, L., Cao, Z., & Xiao, Y. (2017). DeepCloud: Ground-Based Cloud Image Categorization Using Deep Convolutional Features. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 55(10), 5729–5740. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2017.2712809>
- Zhang, J., Liu, P., Zhang, F., & Song, Q. (2018). CloudNet: Ground-Based Cloud Classification With Deep Convolutional Neural Network. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 45(16), 8665–8672. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL077787>
- Zhu, W., Chen, T., Hou, B., Bian, C., Yu, A., Chen, L., Tang, M., & Zhu, Y. (2022). Classification of Ground-Based Cloud Images by Improved Combined Convolutional Network. *Applied Sciences*, 12(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12031570>